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PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION AS THE MAIN TYPE OF SOCIAL MANAGEMENT, THE FIELD OF SCIENTIFIC KNOWLEDGE AND THE FIELD OF EDUCATION

ПУБЛІЧНЕ УПРАВЛІННЯ ЯК ОСНОВНИЙ РІЗНОВИД СОЦІАЛЬНОГО УПРАВЛІННЯ, ГАЛУЗЬ НАУКОВОГО ЗНАННЯ І ГАЛУЗЬ ОСВІТИ

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Добрянська Н.А., Арбузова А.С., Мазілкина О.О. Публічне управління як основний різновид соціального управління, галузь наукового знання і галузь освіти. Оглядова стаття.

Стаття присвячена визначенню ролі та значення публічного управління у світі. Розглянуто публічне управління як основний різновид управління та галузь освіти, навчальна дисципліна. Детально розкрито зміст поняття публічного управління та адміністрування, менеджменту. Визначено та опрацьовано можливості та методи публічного управління, форми публічного управління. Предметом дослідження є теоретичні, методологічні основи і практичні аспекти публічного управління.

Ключові слова: публічне управління, публічне адміністрування, управлінська діяльність, менеджмент, державна влада

Dobrianska N.A., Arbuzova A.S., Mazilkina O.O. Public administration as the main type of social management, the field of scientific knowledge and the field of education. Review article.

The article is devoted to defining the role and importance of public administration in the world. Public administration is considered as the main type of management and branch of education, academic discipline. The content of the concept of public administration and management is revealed in detail. Possibilities and methods of public administration, forms of public administration are defined and worked out. The subject of research is the theoretical, methodological foundations and practical aspects of public administration.

Keywords: public administration, public administration, managerial activity, management, state power

Public administration is a scientific discipline of modern post-industrial, information technology society, which became institutional in Ukraine in the first years of its independence. Various changes in the system of public relations have become urgent challenges for public administration, associated with the emergence of social, economic and environmental conflicts. Public administration as the main type of social management has specific features that exclude the possibility of their identification, in most cases acting on behalf of the state. Public administration, as a branch of science and education, is the only specialty in Ukraine that provides all the competencies for large-scale management. Specialty 281 "Public Administration" provides unique opportunities and fundamental prospects for all who have chosen it. It is this specialty that makes it possible to obtain a profession that, without exaggeration, will always be relevant and in demand.

Analysis of recent research and publications

The problem of evaluating the effectiveness of public administration today remains one of the most pressing, some aspects of which are devoted to a number of works of scientific and analytical nature. A number of scientific works, in particular Bakumenko V.D., are devoted to the research of theoretical bases of estimation of efficiency of public administration [4], Bosak O.Z. [8], Voitovich R.V. [6], Mamonov I.L. [3], Skidan O.V. [10]. It is worth noting the scientific work of M. Shevchenko and A. Pelykh [1], which focuses on the study of methodological approaches to assessing the effectiveness of the state mechanism for responding to threats to national interests and identified, as a result, a pragmatic approach as the most promising; it is proposed to distinguish between the general and current effectiveness of the state mechanism for responding to threats to national interests.

The main part

Today, one of the problems of public administration as an educational and scientific field is the formation of a single integrated terminological system of public administration. This is primarily due to the fact that a large number of terms used by different authors contradict each other [2]. Society is a complex dynamic system; the basis of its social structure are social groups and social institutions. To ensure the viability of society creates conditions for the functioning of amateur bases of various structural elements, their self-regulatory interactions to external influences in order to achieve optimal results in their activities. Self-regulatory processes require the development of self-government, a component of which is management activities [3].

V. Bakumenko researched the scientific bases of formation of state-administrative decisions, proposed general and problem-oriented approaches and methods of improving their formation [4], N. Nyzhnyk revealed the basic laws and forms of legal regulation of state-administrative relations and identified ways to increase their efficiency [5]. R. Voitovych conducted a conceptual analysis of global integration, specified levels, forms and means of modernization of public administration in these conditions [6], A. Rachynsky proposed a new strategic approach to understanding the nature of staff and organization of the management process, and introduced optimization technologies for strategic management personnel in the system of public authorities. The term "public administration" can be used in at least three basic meanings: the activities of civil servants and politicians, the structure and procedures of public authorities, the systematic study of either activities or structures and procedures.

The term "public administration", which replaced the term "public administration", was first used by the English civil servant Desmond Keeling in 1972 [7]. "Public administration is the search for the best way to use resources to achieve priority public policy goals". The emergence of a new form of public administration has been driven by the need to modernize the organizational structures and procedures they use in order for all public institutions to work better. Public administration concerns the effective functioning of the entire system of political institutions [8].

According to the content, the types of public administration are divided into the following:

- provision of administrative services by the public administration, as a result of which the human-centrist ideology of modern administrative law is most fully realized, when the public administration must fully satisfy the rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of individuals and legal entities. Example: administrative service centers of local executive bodies and local self-government entities provide hundreds of different administrative services to individuals and legal entities under a single window system;
- implementation of executive-administrative (management) activities, in the process of which the public administration carries out public implementation of legislation throughout the state in accordance with clearly defined competence and issues for this purpose bylaws on the basis of laws and for their implementation through detailing and specification. Example of executive activity: the patrol police is obliged to take all measures provided by law to prevent violations of the rights and freedoms of citizens in public places, in particular to prevent hooliganism, damage to communal property, violation of environmental regulations. An example of administrative activities to implement the laws of Ukraine: in order to ensure the proper functioning of territorial patrol services by order of 03.07.2015 № 777 MIA of Ukraine approved the "Regulations on the patrol service of the MIA", which defines the tasks, main directions languages and rights of patrol officers of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine.

In the direction of the authoritative influence of public administration:

- external administrative activity of public administration;
 - internal organizational activities of public administration.
- By legal consequences for objects of administrative influence:
- interfering public administration, associated with a clearly defined by law restriction of the rights, freedoms or legitimate interests of an individual, which is manifested in the imposition of appropriate responsibilities or burdens. Example: a police officer may use physical force, including special means of combat (hand-to-hand combat), to stop an offense and detain the person who committed such an offense;
 - favorable public administration, which aims to assist individuals in exercising their rights, freedoms or legitimate interests. It is associated with the provision of services, permits, benefits, certificates to individuals by public administration entities. Example: administrative service centers provide more than 250 different administrative services, including: permission to place outdoor advertising; permission to hold events involving animals; registration and issuance of a passport of a citizen of Ukraine;
 - provisional administrative proceedings related to ensuring the normal existence of individuals and aimed at addressing issues related to providing the population with water, electricity, gas; providing information and educational services, as well as providing prosthetics, housing and other social benefits for participants in anti-terrorist operations, the disabled, large families, etc. Example: The Government of Ukraine has allocated UAH 30 million from the state budget for the program to purchase affordable housing in 2017; participants in anti-terrorist operations and internally displaced persons had the primary right to use it;
 - a separate line in this system defines the activities of public administration entities for the development of infrastructure facilities – construction of subways, highways, railways, airports, recreation parks, sports facilities, etc. Example: before the European Football Championship in 2012, stadiums, airports, railway

stations and others were built and reconstructed at the expense of the state (UAH 40 billion, or \$ 5 billion) and local budgets (UAH 3,7 billion). infrastructure facilities.

Thus, the main types of public administration are as follows: the provision of administrative services by the public administration and the implementation of executive and administrative (management) activities (in content); external and internal administrative activities of public administration (in the direction of the authoritative influence of public administration); interfering, facilitating and providing administrative proceedings (for legal consequences for objects of administrative influence) [9].

Public administration opportunities are limited. Only some common issues can be resolved through the use of public authority. Some differences will always exist, without this the development of society is impossible. Applying measures of managerial influence, it is impossible to eliminate social and other conflicts in society [10].

Capabilities of public administration are related to four factors: will, power, strength and material resources. Being to some extent separated from the public collective, its bodies have a special will, different from the will of its constituent members, and sometimes even contradicts the will of the collective itself.

Regulation of public relations in the public team has its limits. It is believed that the state and other public authorities should not interfere in the sphere of civil society, regulate relations in this area.

First, they are limited by the very nature of the object of regulation

Secondly, the limits of regulation "from above" are set by the society itself, another public collective, the natural self-regulation of the collective.

Third, the boundaries of public administration put the real possibilities of society.

One of the main tasks of management (regulation) is to comply with the necessary proportions, so as not to exceed the socially acceptable "threshold".

Public administration is a rule-making, administrative, control, organizational and other activity. It is carried out on the basis of established norms, rules, procedures. These rules must be followed by public administration bodies, state officials, federation entities, and autonomous entities.

Normative regulation is the regulation of people's behavior by means of normative legal acts designed for their repeated application in the presence of the circumstances provided by them. That is, the scope of public relations, which is subject to regulatory legal regulation, is quantitatively uncertain [11].

There are many different rules in society that are used in management. Moral norms play a significant role. Violation of moral norms is not punished by the state, it causes only public condemnation, but their impact is especially great where management is associated with public policy (e.g., failure to fulfill promises made by the head of state, government, deputies, unethical public behavior of senior officials). Trust and objective information, observance of moral requirements by managers and subordinates are necessary at all levels of the civil service, as well as between managers and managers at all levels of public administration.

Customs are used in public administration, sometimes centuries-old traditions operate. The huge role in management is played by the standards established by the state, the technical rules necessary in production activity, in trade (including with foreign countries). Organizational norms and customs are formed in the activity of state bodies and institutions. They are used, for example, in the reports of elected officials to citizens (choice of time, place for the report, the order of the meeting, etc.).

Forms of public administration must meet the following requirements:

- not to go beyond the rule of law;
- correspond to the competencies of the subject of public administration;
- comply with the content of its administrative obligations;
- correspond to the content and nature of the issues to be addressed;
- to promote the satisfaction of the public interest;
- take into account the features of a particular object of power [12].

Figure 1 presents the forms of management.

Figure 1. Forms of management
Source: authors' own development

Forms of public administration can be classified on various grounds:

By the degree of legal expression:

- basic (publication of legal acts);

- derivatives are based on them, i.e., various actions that entail certain legal consequences that have a certain legal orientation (registration, permitting, supervisory, preventive, security actions, etc.);
- According to the achieved results:
 - positive regulation (approval of socio-economic development programs, publication of regulations on public authorities, etc.);
 - reaction to negative phenomena in public administration (application of measures of administrative responsibility);
- By orientation:
 - affecting public relations in the field of public administration (external);
 - influencing the internal management activities of structural units of public administration (internal);
- By the number of persons to whom they apply:
 - mandatory;
 - addressed to specific entities;
- By the nature and methods of solving competence issues:
 - procedural (for example, preparation and adoption of management decisions)
 - procedural (for example, in the framework of administrative-sensitive proceedings);
- By subject composition:
 - unilateral;
 - bilateral or multilateral (administrative agreements);
- By the subject of the initiative:
 - those carried out by the public administration on its own initiative by virtue of the requirements of the competence assigned to them;
 - those used by the public administration on the initiative of other entities (for example, on appeals (applications, complaints) of individuals and legal entities);
- Under the conditions of application:
 - under normal conditions of public life;
 - in a state of emergency;
- By legal content:
 - binding;
 - prohibiting;
 - allowing. In the legal literature there are other grounds for the classification of forms of public administration, but the most common are two classifications: 1) the significance of the consequences that arise as a result of the use of one or another form (the presence of a legal effect); 2) the degree of legal regulation of the process of their application.
- According to the value of the consequences that arise as a result of the use of forms are:
 - legal forms of public administration;
 - non-legal forms of public administration.
- Legal forms include forms, the use of which causes legal consequences. In particular, the issuance of legal acts, the application of coercive measures, etc. Such forms act as legal facts and can form administrative-legal relations. Non-legal forms include forms that do not have direct legal significance and do not cause the emergence of administrative-legal relations. Such forms either precede the legal one (conducting an audit based on the results of which a legal act is issued), or are used according to them (meeting on the implementation of the legal act).
- According to the degree of legal regulation of the process of use, the following forms of public administration are distinguished:
 - establishment of legal norms (publication of normative acts of public administration);
 - application of legal norms (publication of non-normative acts of public administration, acts of application of legal norms);
 - concluding administrative agreements;
 - implementation of registration and other legally significant actions;
 - carrying out organizational actions;
 - execution of logistical operations.
- The first four forms are legal, the rest are non-legal. This division of forms of public administration most fully reflects the activities of public administration, its breadth and specificity [13; 22].
- Along with the forms of public administration in the process of practical implementation of administrative obligations of public administration an important role is given to the methods of its activities.
- In the conventional sense, the method means a method, a method of practical implementation of something. With regard to the activities of public administration, it means a method, a method of practical implementation by its subjects of tasks and functions in everyday activities on the basis of the competence assigned to them, within the established limits and in the appropriate form. This category is therefore directly related to the characteristics of the essence of public administration, being one of its essential elements [14; 23].

Administrative management has a wide scope. It is carried out on a national scale, at the local level, in a particular team, government agencies and officials inside and outside. Management can also be carried out on different scales, but it has a different nature. These are the actions of the leader within a certain team, as well as outside on behalf of this team and in its interests. Management may include methods of administration, but they are not the main thing in this process.

Administration in public administration is necessary, without it is impossible to solve many questions (especially in public collective on military or paramilitary discipline, for example, in army, militia). Acts of administration may have different content and different mode of action. They can be adopted taking into account the requirements of life, when all the conditions and all the consequences of such acts are taken into account. Otherwise, administrative acts of a voluntaristic nature are adopted. This is the "naked" administration, when teams are given without taking into account the existing realities (for example, to abolish economic ministries and create closed within certain regions advice on the national economy, pursue a friendly policy towards some countries, guided by subjective preconditions, and be in constant confrontation with others, etc.).

The word "management" is based on the Latin root: manus – hand. Management techniques are used in various areas of management (for the management of the enterprise, institution, public association, etc.). Management in public administration has its peculiarities, arising primarily from the fact that the manager (the subject of management, which in some cases may be a state, municipal or other body, but more often an official) has powers derived from public authority. Although this power is different in public administration and local self-government, it is always the most important resource of a manager, including psychologically. The manager does not always use his powers (authority), sometimes preferring other ways of influencing (for example, personal authority as a capable, skilled, knowledgeable person).

Unlike public administration, which can extend to the country as a whole, a particular region, public management usually has a narrower sphere of influence and a more specific nature. The usual field of management is a relatively small team (although it can be an enterprise with thousands of workers, and an area with a population of millions, and the state and an international association). The object of management can be a team whose work the manager wants to improve, an individual employee, from whom he seeks perseverance and accuracy, the office process, which he wants to reduce. Less often, the object of personal management is the entire society or the international community. For large teams, other management methods are preferred. Management, regardless of whether power is used, usually has certain personal aspects. Often a personal connection of the manager with the object of management, ultimately with the employees who form the personnel basis of the object, with the population of the territory is necessary. The activities of the manager include the formation of psychological attitudes, the creation of good personal relationships in the teams of state and municipal government. Not authoritative orders, but the human factor plays an important role in the activities of the manager. The most common goal of management in team management - to increase the organization, order, efficiency of the team [15; 19].

Today in the labor market there is an urgent need for professionals who have the management skills necessary to provide administrative services in the public sphere, who are familiar with the principles, functions and ethics of official activity in public authorities and local governments.

Training in bachelor's and master's degree programs in Public Administration is aimed at training highly qualified specialists to work in the field of public administration, local self-government and the business sector, which provide the European level of administrative and management services. Specialists are trained to solve strategic management problems in the public and corporate sectors, taking into account a set of external and internal factors of influence and development trends in a competitive environment in a particular area of social production and the state as a whole. Future specialists can work in public authorities, local governments and public organizations. The competitive advantages of the specialty "Public Administration" are to provide applicants with the necessary competencies in public administration [16, 18; 20].

The main purpose of the discipline is the formation of knowledge about the structure and features of the functioning of public administration and administration. The study will provide skills in solving problems to improve the efficiency of public administration and administration and solving practical problems of administrative management, which involves the application of theories and scientific methods of public administration through administrative mechanisms and tools of civil society. Applicants for higher education will get acquainted with the best domestic and foreign practices of public authorities, as well as study the main regulations and provisions of legislation governing the field of public administration. During the study of the discipline applicants for higher education:

- gain skills in strategic planning, adaptation and action in a new situation, taking into account changing socio-economic and political conditions of the state;
- acquire skills to work in a team as part of a working group to conduct applied research while performing practical tasks to optimize the functioning of public authorities;
- master the skills of planning and time management and controlling as a modern concept of administrative management;
- master the skills to identify, pose and solve problems of institutional support for the formation and implementation of state social policy in Ukraine;

- gain skills to ensure the appropriate level of development and use of management products, services or processes to stimulate economic development of the state through the tools of e-democracy and civil society development;
- master the skills of realization of their rights and responsibilities as a member of society, the ability to take into account the values of civil (free democratic) society and the need for its sustainable political and legal mechanism of development in Ukraine;
- gain skills in critical and self-critical thinking on the basis of normative-legal and moral-ethical norms of behavior with an understanding of the history and patterns of development of public power both in Ukraine and abroad;
- gain skills in developing tactical and operational management plans in public authorities;
- acquire skills in research and exploration, processing and analysis of information, their systematization by regulations issued by public authorities;
- get acquainted with foreign experience in the use of various information and communication technologies used in the process of preparation and implementation of management decisions in public authorities. The discipline "Public Administration" has an interdisciplinary nature and integrates knowledge from other educational and scientific fields: public administration and administration, management, law, etc. [17; 21].

Conclusion

Public administration is a type of socially useful activity carried out by a certain set of entities, including public authorities, local governments, etc. Customs are used in public administration, sometimes centuries-old traditions operate. The huge role in management is played by the standards established by the state, the technical rules necessary in production activity, in trade (including with foreign countries). The subject of study of the discipline "Public Administration" is the process of achieving public goals by the use of public administration administrative methods of influencing public processes, defined by instructions, regulations, procedures and more.

In the activities of public administration, methods are the most important remedy. Their use must be carried out in a rational combination, taking into account the characteristics of the objects of influence, field of activity, material capabilities, human and technical potential, to help reduce obstacles to the exercise of citizens' rights, freedoms and legitimate interests.

Administrative management has a wide scope. It is carried out on a national scale, at the local level, in a particular team, government agencies and officials inside and outside. Management can also be carried out on different scales, but it has a different nature. These are the actions of the leader within a certain team, as well as outside on behalf of this team and in its interests. Management may include methods of administration, but they are not the main thing in this process. Training in bachelor's and master's degree programs in Public Administration is aimed at training highly qualified specialists to work in the field of public administration, local self-government and the business sector, which provide the European level of administrative and management services. The main purpose of the discipline "Public Administration" is the formation of knowledge about the structure and features of the functioning of public administration. The study will provide skills in solving problems to improve the efficiency of public administration and administration and solving practical problems of administrative management, which involves the application of theories and scientific methods of public administration through administrative mechanisms and tools of civil society.

Abstract

Public administration is a scientific discipline of modern post-industrial, information technology society, which became institutional in Ukraine in the first years of its independence. The term "public administration", which replaced the term "public administration", was first used by the English civil servant Desmond Keeling in 1972. "Public administration is the search for the best way to use resources to achieve priority public policy goals." The main types of public administration are as follows: the provision of administrative services by the public administration and the implementation of executive and administrative activities (in content); external and internal administrative activities of public administration (in the direction of the authoritative influence of public administration); interfering, facilitating and providing administrative proceedings (for legal consequences for objects of administrative influence).

Possibilities of public administration are connected with four factors: will, the power, force and material resources. Regulation of public relations in public collective has the limits. It is believed that the state and other public authorities should not interfere in the sphere of civil society, regulate relations in this area. There are many different rules in society that are used in management. Moral norms play a significant role. Violation of moral norms is not punished by the state, it causes only public condemnation, but their impact is especially great where management is associated with public policy (e.g., failure to fulfill promises made by the head of state, government, deputies, unethical public behavior of senior officials).

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Training in bachelor's and master's degree programs in Public Administration is aimed at training highly qualified specialists to work in the field of public administration, local self-government and the business sector, which provide the European level of administrative and management services. The main purpose of the discipline is the formation of knowledge about the structure and features of the functioning of public administration and administration. The discipline "Public Administration" has an interdisciplinary nature and integrates knowledge from other educational and scientific fields: public administration and administration, management, law, etc.

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